

QPRT

(quinolinate phosphoribosyltransferase)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	23475 / Q15274
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
TREAT-AD Authors	Katerina Gospodinova ¹ , Ishita Ajith ¹ , Benjamin Siciliano ² , Qianjin Li ² , Jesse Wiley ³ , Gregory Cary ⁴ , YCharOS ⁵ , Souvika Bakshi ¹ , Richard Nwakamma ² , Elizabeth Zoeller ² , Ranjita Betarbet ² , Vittorio Katis ¹ , Allan Levey ² , Zhexing Wen ² , Haian Fu ² , Paul Brennan ¹ , and the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center
Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
Document version	2.0
Document version date	February 2024
Citation	10.5281/zenodo.7968422 .
Affiliations	¹ Centre for Medicines Discovery, University of Oxford, Oxford, United Kingdom ² Emory University, Atlanta, GA, USA ³ Sage Bionetworks, Seattle, WA, USA ⁴ The Jackson Laboratory, Bar Harbor, ME, USA ⁵ YCharOS, McGill University, Montreal, Canada

USEFUL LINKS

TREAT-AD

[Visit TREAT-AD](#)

Learn more about the TREAT-AD centers and mission

Agora

[Visit Agora](#)

View Alzheimer's disease target results explorer

AD Knowledge Portal

[Visit AD Knowledge Portal](#)

View available target enabling resources

CONTENTS OF TEP

Bioinformatic analysis: Target source & hypothesis

Validated antibodies & generic knockout cell lines: YCharOS antibody characterization report

Protein constructs & expression methods: Full-length expressed in SF9 cells

Cell type specific expression: lysates and media from hiPSC derived neurons, astrocytes, and microglia

Biological probe discovery: characterization of immunodepletion and treatment with recombinant protein in cell models

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

For more information or questions regarding the TEP, please contact treatad.info@sagebionetworks.org

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 4.03 (rank #307, 98.8th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target’s general relevance to Alzheimer’s Disease, and is the sum of the target’s Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 4.03 out of 5 (rank #307, 98.8th percentile). The individual score components include 2.05 of 3 for genetics, and 1.98 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of QPRT expression, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. QPRT is

annotated to the GO term “NAD metabolic process” from the Mitochondrial Metabolism biological domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer’s Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no

dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression. The expression of QPRT is not confidently detected in any cell type within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

QPRT is a core enzyme involved in the conversion of tryptophan to NAD which was identified in deep proteomic studies of the human brain to be associated with AD pathology and cognitive decline (see below for details and citations). The goal of this TEP is to provide the scientific community with high quality resources that may help identify specific disease linked processes. The contents of this TEP include bioinformatic analysis, protein structural information and purified protein, and validated antibodies for QPRT investigations. We hope these resources facilitate the efficiency and accuracy of future work in the field.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Quinolate phosphoribosyltransferase (QPRT) is the rate limiting enzyme in the conversion of tryptophan to NAD (1), a key component of the mitochondrial TCA cycle, which breaks down the neurotoxic quinolate intermediate (2–4). QPRT is part of the 32 gene set comprising module 42 (M42) that was identified by large scale deep proteomics of the human brain in AD case-control studies (5). M42 was selected for investigation due to the robust correlation with AD-linked pathology (global pathology, CERAD, and Braak scores) and cognitive performance (MMSE and global measures)(5). M42 underwent significant change from the asymptomatic cases with AD pathology but lacking a clinical diagnosis, suggesting that it was changing in advance of cognitive decline, and consequently a potentially a driver of disease pathogenesis (5). However, it is also distinctly plausible that increased levels of QPRT coincide with neuronal preservation attempts, changing NAD levels in order to achieve neuronal homeostasis. Consistent with this possibility, knocking out QPRT in mice correlates with increases in amyloid in the hippocampus (6). Previous studies with QPRT had already identified a role in mediating survival, as QPRT appears to be important in buffering glial lineages (and potentially neurons) from oxidative stress (1,7). QPRT inhibitors facilitate the sensitization of gliomas to oxidative damage (1,7). QPRT is expressed in both the parahippocampal gyrus and the hippocampus (8,9), and some of the earliest investigations of the cloned gene identified that it increased in accordance with neuronal degeneration (10,11). While there is little direct data delineating a precise role of QPRT in AD, there is compelling circumstantial evidence to suggest a plausible involvement in neurodegeneration, as regulation of oxidative state is critical to neuronal survival and plays a key role mediation of several components of mitochondrial metabolism.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Validated Antibodies & Generic Knockout Cell Lines

The YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for QPRT. The YCharOS antibody characterization pipeline uses knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of available commercial antibodies for QPRT by immunoblot (Western blot), immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. The cell line background was chosen based on the adequate expression of the target protein.

[QPRT antibody characterization report](#)

Proteins Purified

1. QPRTA-c002: Human QPRT1 (E1-E297). Contains a C-terminal 6His. Protein produced in SF9 cells.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

Cell type specific expression: Using anti-human QPRT antibody ab171944 as appears in the [YCharOS QPRT Antibody Characterization Report](#), QPRT expression was easily detected in human iPSC-derived neurons, astrocytes, and microglia (Fig. 1). See **Additional Information** for cell line information, iPSC differentiation protocols, and Western blot conditions.

Figure 1. Expression of QPRT in whole cell lysates (top) and media (bottom) across neurons (N), astrocytes (A), and microglia (M) derived from iPSC cell lines WTC11 (left) and F033K (right). Independent samples ($n=2$) were run in adjacent lanes.

Biological probe discovery:

- 1) **Immunodepletion of secreted protein in medium** : QPRT was immunoprecipitated from media conditioned with WTC11-derived neurons. QPRT was measured in eluate following immunoprecipitation by Western blot and unbound QPRT was detected in flowthrough by Western blot and ELISA (Fig. 2). See **Additional Information** for experimental information on immunoprecipitation, Western blotting, and ELISAs.

Figure 2. Immunoprecipitation (IP) of QPRT using validated antibody ab171944 from iPSC-derived neuron conditioned media. Western blot of eluted QPRT (top) and unbound QPRT in flowthrough (bottom) from media samples, $n=3$ technical replicates of single sample collection loaded in three adjacent lanes.

- 2) **Cell-based assays following immunodepletion:** To understand the impact of modulating QPRT on cell function, we performed a small panel of assays on cells treated with anti-QPRT antibody. WTC11 iPSC-derived neurons were treated with anti-QPRT before measuring $A\beta_{40}$ and $A\beta_{42}$ in conditioned media (Fig. 3). iPSC-derived astrocytes were treated with anti-QPRT before measuring IL-6 in conditioned media (Fig. 4). Treatment with anti-QPRT increased $A\beta_{42}$ levels in iPSC-neurons

and increased IL-6 levels in iPSC-astrocytes (ns). See **Additional Information** for experimental information.

Figure 3. Immunodepletion of QPRT from iPSC derived neurons by treatment with anti-QPRT antibody. IL-6 levels in WTC11 astrocyte conditioned media when treated with anti-QPRT antibody or IgG as measured by ELISA, n=2 independent experiments * $p < 0.05$ and ns= $p > 0.05$

Figure 4. Immunodepletion of QPRT from iPSC derived astrocytes by treatment with anti-QPRT antibody. IL-6 levels in WTC11 astrocyte conditioned media when treated with anti-QPRT antibody or IgG as measured by ELISA, n=2 independent experiments. ** $p < 0.01$.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of QPRT in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Protein expression constructs and protein purification

All relevant plasmids are available on Addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

1. QPRTA-c002: Human QPRT1 (E1-E297). Contains a C-terminal 6His. Protein produced in SF9 cells.

Construct ID	QPRTA-c002
Parental vector	pFastBac1
Tag	C-terminal His6
Protein mass (with tag and secretion signal)	32621.5 Da
Extinction Coefficient ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	27960
Protein sequence (with tag)	MDAEG LALLPPVTLAALVDSWLREDCPGLNYAALVSGAGPSQAALWAKSPGVLGQPFF DAIFTQLNCQVSWFLPEGSKLVPVARVAEVRGPAHCLLLGERVALNLTARCSGIASAAAAAV EAARGAGWTGHVAGTRKTTGFRLEKYGLLVGGAASHRYDLGGLVMVKDNHVVAAGGV EKAVRAARQAADFTLKVEVECSSLQEAQAAEAGADLVLLDNFKPEELHPTATVLKAQFPSV AVEASGGITLDNLPQFCGPHIDVISMGMLTQAAPALDFSLKLFKEVAPVPKIHAENLYFQSH HHHHH

For more information or questions regarding the TEP, please contact treatad.info@sagebionetworks.org

Intact Mass Deconvolution: QPRTA-c002 (with tag)	N/A
Observed Mass:	N/A
Protein yield:	2.3 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>Insect</i> : Sf9 cells (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Expression medium	Sf900-II SFM Medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Virus generation	For transposition, transform construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain DH10Bac. Plate on LB-agar plates containing kanamycin (50 µg/ml), gentamycin (7 µg/ml), tetracycline (10 µg/ml), IPTG (40 µg/ml) and bluogal (300 µg/ml). Inoculate 5 ml LB broth containing kanamycin (50 µg/ml), gentamycin (7 µg/ml) and tetracycline (10 µg/ml) with a single colony and grow overnight at 37°C with shaking. Perform MiniPrep (Millipore) according to manufacturer's instructions. Add 1 volume of isopropanol to precipitate the bacmid DNA. Spin (13000g, 20 min, 4°C) and wash pellet with 70% ethanol. Resuspend bacmid with sterile TE buffer under sterile conditions.
Transfection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Transfect Sf9 cells at a density of 2×10^6 cells/ml. 2. Just before infection, add 2% FBS to the cells. 3. Infect the cells with 120 µl of P0 Baculovirus stock and incubate at 27°C, with shaking at 450 rpm in a Glas-Col shaker for 66-72 h and harvest P1 baculovirus. 4. Pellet the cells by centrifugation at 1500 x g for 20 min and harvest the supernatant. Repeat steps 2 and 3, then infect the cells with 120 µl of P1 baculovirus stock and incubate at 27°C, with shaking at 450 rpm in a Glas-Col shaker for 66-72 h. Pellet the cells by centrifugation at 900 x g for 30 min for purification.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ni IMAC W10 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 2. Ni IMAC W25 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 25 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 3. Ni IMAC elution buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 200 mM NaCl, 250 mM imidazole, 2% glycerol 4. Size exclusion chromatography elution buffer : dPBS (from ThermoFisher) 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Ni IMAC W10 buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Thaw pellet and resuspend to 40ml LB. 2. Sonicate at amplitude 35%, pulse 5s on/ 10s off, 20 minutes. 3. Centrifuge at 22,000g 30 mins. Decant cleared supernatant. 4. Add 3ml equilibrated Ni-sepharose beads and bind for 1h with rotation at 4°C. 5. Spin at 700g for 5 mins and decant the supernatant. 6. Spin beads/lysate slurry (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant supernatant and wash beads with 100 ml W10 buffer. Repeat wash with 50 ml W10. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 7. Wash column with 25 ml W25.

	8. Elute protein with 1x 10 ml elution buffer, followed by 2x5 ml elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. Pool elution fractions containing protein.
Purification step 2: Size Exclusion Chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate pooled IMAC elution fractions to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Perform SEC on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column, equilibrated in DPBS, at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 1-5 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

Cell line information

The familial Alzheimer's disease (fAD) iPSC line (F033K) was previously generated from fibroblasts of a patient carrying the APP V717I (London) mutation (12). The well-characterized WTC11 iPSC line (13) and the F033K line were cultured in mTeSR1 medium (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 85850) on cell culture treated dishes coated with Geltrex LDEV-Free Reduced Growth Factor Basement Membrane Matrix (Gibco/Thermo Fisher Scientific; Cat. No. A1413201) diluted 1:100 in DMEM/F-12 (Gibco/Thermo Fisher Scientific; Cat. No. 11320033). Briefly, mTeSR1 was replaced every other day or every day once 50% confluent. When 80-90% confluent, cells were passaged, which entailed the following: aspirating media, washing with DPBS, incubating with ReLeSR (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0484) at RT for 3 minutes, aspirating ReLeSR, and incubating at 37°C for 10 minutes, resuspending in mTeSR1 supplemented with 10nM Y-27632 dihydrochloride ROCK inhibitor (Tocris; Cat. No. 125410), counting, and plating onto Matrigel-coated plates at desired number.

iPSC differentiation protocols

Astrocytes: Human iPSC-derived astrocytes (iAs) were generated as previously described (14). Briefly, iPSCs were plated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates and infected with rtTA, SOX9, and NFIB lentivirus. On Day 0, medium was replaced with fresh mTeSR-1 medium containing 2.5 µg/mL doxycycline. From Day 1-7, iAs were cultured in expansion medium (DMEM/F12, 10% FBS, 1% N2, 1.25 µg/mL puromycin, 200 µg/mL Hygromycin) and gradually transitioned to FGF medium (Neurobasal, 2% B27, 1% NEAA, 1% GlutaMax, 1% FBS, 8 ng/mL FGF, 5 ng/mL CNTF, 10 ng/mL BMP4, 200 µg/mL Hygromycin) by Day 7. On Day 7, iAs were dissociated using Accutase for 10 minutes, and replated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates in FGF medium. From Day 9, FGF medium was changed to Maturation medium (1:1 DMEM/F12 and Neurobasal, 1% N2, 1% Na Pyruvate, 10 µg/µL NAC, 10 µg/µL hbEGF, 10 ng/mL CNTF, 10 ng/mL BMP4, 500 µg/mL cAMP) and half of the medium was changed every 2 to 3 days.

Neurons: Human iPSC-derived neurons (iNs) were generated as previously described (15). Briefly, iPSCs were plated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates and infected with rtTA and NGN2 lentivirus. On Day 0, medium was replaced with fresh mTeSR-1 medium containing 2.5 µg/mL doxycycline. From Day 1-3, iNs were cultured in K2B medium (KO DMEM, 15% KSR, 1% NEAA, 0.1% BME, 1% GlutaMax, 2 µg/ml doxycycline) and gradually transitioned to N2B medium (DMEM/F12, 1% GlutaMax, 1.5% dextrose, 1% N2, 2 µg/ml doxycycline, 1 µg/mL puromycin) by Day 3. On Day 4, iNs were dissociated using Accutase for 5 minutes, and replated on Matrigel-coated 6-well plates in NBM medium (Neurobasal, 1% GlutaMax, 1.5% dextrose, 0.5% NEAA, 2% B27, 10 ng/ml BDNF, 10 ng/ml GDNF, 10 ng/ml CNTF, 2 µg/ml doxycycline, 1µg/mL puromycin) and half of the medium was changed every 2 to 3 days.

Microglia: Human iPSC-derived microglia-like cells (iMGL) were generated by first differentiating human iPSCs into hematopoietic progenitor cells using the STEMdiff Hematopoietic Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 05310) per manufacturer's instructions. Then, hematopoietic progenitor cells were differentiated into microglia using the STEMdiff Microglia Differentiation Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0019) and matured using STEMdiff Microglia Maturation Kit (STEMCELL Technologies; Cat. No. 100-0020) following the manufacturer's instructions.

Western blotting

Media were collected and spun at 5000 X g for 10 min. The supernatants were stored at -80°C. For Western blotting, 1/3 volume of 4x Laemmli protein sample buffer (BioRad, 1610747) was added to culture media. After boiling at 98°C for 5 min. For cell lysate collection, after removing media, cells were washed with PBS twice and collected in PBS with a cell

scraper. Cells were spun at 3000 rpm for 5 min, and the supernatants were discarded. Cells were lysed in NP-40 buffer (1% nonidet P-40, 20 mM Tris (PH 7.4), 137 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol) with protease inhibitor (Sigma, P8340) and phosphatase inhibitor (Sigma, P5726 and P0044). 1/3 volume of 4x Laemmli protein sample buffer (BioRad, #1610747) was added to lysate and samples were boiled at 98°C for 5 min. For Western blotting, cell culture media and lysates were separated on 10% Tris-glycine SDS-polyacrylamide gels. Proteins were transferred to 0.2 µm nitrocellulose membrane (BioRad, 1620112). The membrane was blocked with 5% non-fat milk for 1 hr and incubated with QPRT antibody (Abcam, ab171944) with 1:1000 dilution in TBST containing 3% BSA at 4°C overnight with gentle rocking. The membrane was washed with TBST for 10 mins three times and then incubated with the secondary antibody (Jackson ImmunoResearch Laboratories, #111-035-003) at 1:5000 at room temperature for 1 hr. After washing with TBST for 10 mins three times, images were taken with the ChemiDoc Imaging System (BioRad, 12003153).

Immunoprecipitation

Cell culture media were collected as described above for Western blotting. QPRT antibody (Abcam, ab171944) was added to media (0.75 µg/ml) and incubated at 4°C overnight with gentle rocking. Protein A/G beads (Santa Cruz, sc-2003) were prewashed with PBS twice and resuspended with lysis buffer after final wash. 30 µl slurry of resuspended beads were added to media which were incubated with the antibody. After two hours incubation at 4°C, beads were pelleted by centrifugation at 3,000 rpm (approximately 1,000xg) for 30 seconds at 4°C. The supernatants were collected to serve as flowthrough. Beads were washed with PBS 3 times. 30-50 ul 2x Laemmli sample buffer (BioRad, 1610737) was added to the beads pellet. After boiling for 5 minutes, samples can be stored at -20°C for Western blotting.

Immunodepletion in cell media

QPRT antibody (Abcam, ab171944) was added to media (0.75 µg/ml) with iPSC derived cells. The cells were further cultured for 3 days at 37°C in humidified conditions with 5% CO₂. Cell culture media were collected as described above for Western blotting. Prewashed protein A/G beads were added to media and incubated at 4°C for two hours. The following steps are the same as immunoprecipitation for cell media described above.

Measurement of Aβ and IL-6

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kits specific for human Aβ₄₀ and Aβ₄₂ (Invitrogen: #KHB3482 and #KHB3441) and IL-6 (R&D Systems: #QK206) were used to quantify Aβ species and IL-6 according to the manufacturer's instructions. Results were expressed as percentages of the isotype control. The means from duplicate measurements are presented.

References

1. Sahm F, Oezen I, Opitz CA, Radlwimmer B, von Deimling A, Ahrendt T, et al. The endogenous tryptophan metabolite and NAD⁺ precursor quinolinic acid confers resistance of gliomas to oxidative stress. *Cancer Res.* 2013 Jun 1;73(11):3225–34.
2. Neves D, Goodfellow BJ, Vieira SI, Silva RM. The role of NAD metabolism in neuronal differentiation. *Neurochem Int.* 2022 Oct;159:105402.
3. Youn HS, Kim TG, Kim MK, Kang GB, Kang JY, Lee JG, et al. Structural Insights into the Quaternary Catalytic Mechanism of Hexameric Human Quinolinic Phosphoribosyltransferase, a Key Enzyme in de novo NAD Biosynthesis. *Sci Rep.* 2016 Jan 25;6:19681.
4. Okuno E, White RJ, Schwarcz R. Quinolinic acid phosphoribosyltransferase: purification and partial characterization from human liver and brain. *J Biochem.* 1988 Jun;103(6):1054–9.
5. Johnson ECB, Dammer EB, Duong DM, Ping L, Zhou M, Yin L, et al. Large-scale proteomic analysis of Alzheimer's disease brain and cerebrospinal fluid reveals early changes in energy metabolism associated with microglia and astrocyte activation. *Nat Med.* 2020 May;26(5):769–80.
6. Toyn JH, Lin XA, Thompson MW, Guss V, Meredith JE, Sankaranarayanan S, et al. Viable mouse gene ablations that robustly alter brain Aβ levels are rare. *BMC Neurosci.* 2010 Nov 5;11:143.
7. Jane EP, Premkumar DR, Thambireddy S, Golbourn B, Agnihotri S, Bertrand KC, et al. Targeting NAD⁺ biosynthesis overcomes panobinostat and bortezomib-induced malignant glioma resistance. *Mol Cancer Res.* 2020 Jul;18(7):1004–17.
8. Fukuoka S, Shibata K. Characterization and functional expression of the cDNA encoding human brain quinolinic phosphoribosyltransferase. *Adv Exp Med Biol.* 1999;467:611–4.

9. Du F, Okuno E, Whetsell WO, Köhler C, Schwarcz R. Distribution of quinolinic acid phosphoribosyltransferase in the human hippocampal formation and parahippocampal gyrus. *J Comp Neurol.* 1990 May 1;295(1):71–82.
10. Speciale C, Okuno E, Schwarcz R. Increased quinolinic acid metabolism following neuronal degeneration in the rat hippocampus. *Brain Res.* 1987 Dec 8;436(1):18–24.
11. Foster AC, Whetsell WO, Bird ED, Schwarcz R. Quinolinic acid phosphoribosyltransferase in human and rat brain: activity in Huntington’s disease and in quinolinate-lesioned rat striatum. *Brain Res.* 1985 Jun 17;336(2):207–14.
12. Kuehner JN, Chen J, Bruggeman EC, Wang F, Li Y, Xu C, et al. 5-hydroxymethylcytosine is dynamically regulated during forebrain organoid development and aberrantly altered in Alzheimer’s disease. *Cell Rep.* 2021 Apr 27;35(4):109042.
13. Miyaoka Y, Chan AH, Judge LM, Yoo J, Huang M, Nguyen TD, et al. Isolation of single-base genome-edited human iPS cells without antibiotic selection. *Nat Methods.* 2014 Mar;11(3):291–3.
14. Canals I, Ginisty A, Quist E, Timmerman R, Fritze J, Miskinyte G, et al. Rapid and efficient induction of functional astrocytes from human pluripotent stem cells. *Nat Methods.* 2018 Sep;15(9):693–6.
15. Zhang Y, Pak C, Han Y, Ahlenius H, Zhang Z, Chanda S, et al. Rapid single-step induction of functional neurons from human pluripotent stem cells. *Neuron.* 2013 Jun 5;78(5):785–98.

We respectfully request that this document is cited using the DOI value as given above if the content is used in your work.